

Insecticidal potential of *Cestrum* sp. (Solanaceae: Solanales) against *Tribolium castaneum* and *Tribolium confusum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera- Tenebrionidae)

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Abstract:

Ethanol extract of plants *Cestrum nocturnum* and *Cestrum diurnum* were studied for their effect on the stored grain pest *Tribolium confusum* and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst). Effect of the plants extract on duration of last instars larval period, % of emergence, weight and mortality of *T. castaneum* and *T. confusum* was evaluated and statistical analysed and graphically presented. Insecticidal effect varies with *cestrum* species. Comparatively alcoholic extract showed remarkable insecticidal activity than the aqueous extract against *Tribolium* sp. Extract incorporated diet when fed to larvae the growth was significantly inhibited. Development of insect was abstracted due to the extracts of *Cestrum* sp. These plant extracts could be useful for controlling the store grain pest *T. castaneum* and *T. confusum*.

Keywords: *Cestrum nocturnum*, *Cestrum diurnum*, *Solanaceae*, *Tribolium*.

Introduction:

Higher plants are a rich source of novel substances that can be used to develop eco-friendly method for insect control (Arnason et al., 1989). Insecticidal activity of many plants against several insect pests has been demonstrated by many researchers (Carlini and Grossi-de-Sá 2002). The deleterious effects of bioactive compounds of plants on insects can be manifested in several manners including mortality, antifeedant, growth inhibitor, suppression of reproductive potential. *Tribolium* species is considered as a major pest of stored grains (Weston and Rattlingourd 2000). The red (*T. castaneum*) and confused (*T. confusum*) flour beetles live in the same environment and compete for resources (Ryan et al., 1970). Control of these insects depends heavily on the use of synthetic insecticides and fumigants. However, their widespread use has led to serious

problems including development of resistance to insecticides, toxic residues on stored grain, and increasing costs of application (Riebeiro et al., 2003). However, there is an urgent need to develop safe alternatives that are of low cost, convenient to use and environmental friendly. Considerable efforts have been focused on plant-derived materials, potentially useful as commercial insecticides. *Cestrum nocturnum* and *Cestrum diurnum* are shrubs used in India as ornamental plants. Patil and Jawale (2002) observed for the first time the Biocidal activities in the leaves of these plants on different organisms.

The aim of our study is to evaluate the insecticidal activity of the ethanol and aqueous extracts from *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* against larvae and adults of *Tribolium sp.* All experiments were simultaneously carried out on the *T. castaneum* and *T. confusum* to verify the potential deference among the species. Weight of larvae; mortality of larvae and adults; larval period duration and adult emergence was assessed in present research.

Material and Methods:

The leaves of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* were obtained from the local gardens and dried at room temperature; finely grounded 100 gram of the powder was washed with petroleum ether and extracted with 1 liter distilled water and ethanol individually. After filtration, the aqueous extract dried at 60°C and ethanol is evaporated with rotary evaporator at 40°C.

The insect eggs of *T. castaneum* and *T. confusum* are brought from the stock culture of *Tribolium* maintained in the Departmental laboratory. Larvae undergoing the experiments are reared and maintained in culture rooms under a temperature of 25°C, with a relative humidity of 70% and 5 hrs photoperiod. A bioassay was design as mention by Jbilou et al., (2006). A control was prepared in the same way without extract application. Five replicates were set up for the treated and control larvae. The weight of each larvae and larval mortality were assessed every two days after treatment. Surviving larvae were studied and recorded for duration of larval period up to pupation and percent of adult emergence at the interval of two days. The mortality of adults, that has emerged from the treated and control larvae, is taken every 4 days.

Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statistica software (Statistica 2004)

Results and Discussion:

The present work revealed the effect of two plant species of genus *Cestrum* on *T. castaneum* and *T. confusum*. Significant insecticidal activity against larvae and adults of *T. castaneum* was observed with crude ethanol extract from *C. nocturnum*, as compare to *C. diurnum*. The larvae were more susceptible than adults to alcoholic extract (Fig.1, 2, 3, 4). Ethanol extracts from the studied species significantly reduces larval growth after just 2 days treatment. The most active species was *C. nocturnum* and most responsive species was *T. castaneum* (Fig. 4, 5). In addition, extract of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* disrupted developmental cycle of larvae by prolonging the duration of the last-instar larvae (Table 1). In this work, it is found that, plant extracts have not induced any mortality in the pupae (Table 1).

Figure 1. Effect of different extracts of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* on cumulative mortality of *T. castaneum* last instar larvae. Bars indicate standard deviation (SD) of observations.

Figure 5. Effect of different extracts of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* on weight (in mg) of *T. castaneum* last instar larvae. Each point represents the mean of 100 larvae \pm SD.

Figure 3. Effect of different extracts of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* cumulative mortality of adult *T. castaneum*. Bars indicate standard deviation (SD) of observations.

Figure 2. Effect of different extracts of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* on cumulative mortality of *T. confusum* last instar larvae. Bars indicate standard deviation (SD) of observations.

Figure 4. Effect of different extracts of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* on cumulative mortality of adult *T. confusum*. Bars indicate standard deviation (SD) of observations.

Figure 6. Effect of different extracts of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* on weight (in mg) of *T. confusum* last instar larvae. each point represent the mean of 100 larvae \pm SD.

This is in agreement with other works. Belles et al., (1985) showed that pupae might exhibit a higher tolerance to chemical agents than active stages. Several compounds isolated from *C. parqui* and *C. diurnum* are potential botanical insecticide agents for the control of lepidopteron, beetles and mosquito larvae. They inhibit larval growth and induce malformed adults (Chaieb et al., 2001, Chaieb et al., 2003, Zapata 2004, 2006, Haouas et al., 2005, Ghosh and Chandra 2006, Ikbal et al., 2006 Ghosh et al., 2008). Aqueous extracts from *C. parqui* showed a high toxicity to neonate larvae when ingested through diet, inhibiting pupation at a concentration above 0.6%. Lower concentrations delayed the larval development and reduced the percentages of pupae formed and adult emergence (Zapata et al., 2006). Crude ethanol extracts of *C. parqui* (Zapata et al., 2004, Chaieb et al., 2001) have been shown to have antifeedant activity against various damaging Lepidoptera.

Table 1. Effect of different extracts of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* on the duration of last instar larval period and % of emergence of *T. castaneum* and *T. confusum*

Plant extract	Larval period (day)		% of emergence	
	<i>T. castaneum</i>	<i>T. confusum</i>	<i>T. castaneum</i>	<i>T. confusum</i>
Control	7.3 \pm 0.14a	8 \pm 0.11	100 \pm 0.00	100 \pm 0.00
<i>C. nocturnum</i> OH	8.4 \pm 0.40b	9.3 \pm 0.40b	91 \pm 2.11b	90 \pm 2.44b
<i>C. nocturnum</i> Aqueous	7.6 \pm 0.18b	8.7 \pm 0.31b	96 \pm 3.12a	97 \pm 3.27b
<i>C. diurnum</i> OH	8.2 \pm 0.14a	9.1 \pm 0.27a	92 \pm 3.23a	91 \pm 3.41a
<i>C. diurnum</i> Aqueous	7.4 \pm 0.21a	8.1 \pm 0.22a	97 \pm 3.00b	98 \pm 3.18a

Each data represent the mean of five replicates, (n=20).

Means within a column followed by the same letter are not significant (Tukey’s HSD test, p<0.05)

The efficacy of the *C. diurnum* as a strong biocontrol agent of the larval *anopheles* mosquito was evaluated by Ghosh and Chandra 2006. Ikbal et al., (2006) experimented with saponin extract of *C. parqui* on *T. confusum*, and revealed a presence of ecdysteroid compound interfering with the development of insect by disrupting the cholesterol metabolism. Babouche et al., (2001) demonstrated that the crude saponin extract is the active fraction in the plant. Saponins interact with dietary cholesterol, and provoke its unavailability for the production of the molting hormone (ecdysone), the reason for saponin toxicity (Arnault and Mauchamp 1986). The other species of *Cestrum* are also found to possess steroidal saponins (Haraguchi et al 2000, Ahmad et al 1993). *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* also possess alkaloids as nicotine and nor nicotine (Halim et al., 1971). Thus, these compounds could be responsible for same effect observed in *T. castaneum* and *T. confusum*. Saponin and other secondary metabolites of these investigated plants may explain the toxic effect in the studied insects.

The investigations of the effects of these pure molecules on *T. castaneum* are in progress. In conclusion, this study put forward that ethanol extract of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum*, plants belonging to families *Solanaceae*, possess toxic principles with significant insecticidal activity and could be a prospective store grain protectant against *Tribolium* sp.

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